

Design and Fabrication of Farming Greenhouses

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Abstract

This master's dissertation explores the automation of repetitive tasks in the design of modular greenhouse structures, with a focus on utilizing Autodesk Inventor and iLogic. Greenhouses, essential for year-round crop cultivation, exhibit a range of geometrical variations, such as single-span and multi-span structures, along with differing tunnel configurations. The modularity of these structures opens the possibilities for automation of the design process through automation of assembly generation.

To understand greenhouse structure, constituent elements, and element variations were systematically analyzed and organized into diagrams. These diagrams served as the foundation for the subsequent development of the external rule within iLogic and Inventor. The primary vehicle for this automation was iLogic, which facilitated access to the Inventor API, thereby enabling the incorporation of Inventor's functionalities into the code.

The outcome of this study is an external rule, that based on user inputs, generates a greenhouse structure within seconds providing better efficiency in the design process. This work aims to contribute to the knowledge about automated assembly generations of complex modular structures with multiple parameters such as greenhouses.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/V62XmtRYYJg>

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10034173